

THE OLDEST SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL MONUMENTS - AS OUR NATIONAL WEALTH AND VALUE.

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Abstract: In this article, the importance of the oldest educational monuments as our national wealth and value is analyzed scientifically.

Keywords: thought of our ancestors, genius, land, history, pedagogy, literature, art, politics, ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, mineralogy, chemistry, architecture, etc.

The spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined without its history, specific customs, traditions, and life values. In this regard, of course, spiritual heritage, cultural assets, old historical monuments serve as one of the most important factors.

The President of our country I. Karimov says about this: "From the oldest petroglyphs and writings created by the thinking and genius of our ancestors, from examples of folk oral creativity, to thousands and thousands of manuscripts kept in the treasury of our libraries today, history, pedagogy, literature, art, politics are embodied in them. , ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, mineralogy, chemistry, architecture and other valuable works are our great spiritual wealth. "It is rare to find a nation with such a great heritage."

The ancestors of the current Uzbek people lived several thousand years ago, and they traveled a long and difficult way to create a high and unique culture. Our history up to the period of the use of the first stone tools for livelihood, the making of much improved work tools, and the achievements in economic life and cultural development by the time of seed production, testify to the fact that our ancestors had a rich ancient culture.

In the first millennium BC, different tribes and peoples lived in the states of Bactria, Khorezm, Sogdiyona, Margyona, Parthia, and Parkana. They consist of tribes and clans such as Sakas, Massagets, Sogdians, Khorezmians, Bakhtars, Chochs, Parkanas, and are considered the ancestors of the peoples living in the territory of the present Central Asia.

In the regions where these peoples lived, their own cultural traditions were formed. For example, in the first half of the century BC, development and progress in various sectors of the national economy took place in the ancient states: Bactria and Sogdiya, Margyona, Khorezm, Parkana, Parthia. Social culture grew in the states of the Ahmonites, which appeared in the 9th-6th centuries BC,

Greco-Bactria, which was formed in the middle of the 3rd century BC, the Kushans, which were formed in the 1st century AD, the Hephthalites, which appeared in the 5th century AD, then the Sassanids, and finally the Turkic Khaganate states.

The educational heritage has a special place in the structure of the ancient culture acquired by our ancestors. After all, the important archaeological findings of modern Turkic and Persian-speaking peoples that have reached us, the creative heritage of historians, literary and artistic figures, and examples of artistic and literary works are proof of this.

Among such important sources are the historical, geographical and moral works of Greek scientists Herodotus, Socrates, Plutarch, Polyenes, our scholars Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mahmud Kashgari, philosopher, orientalist and historical scientists: E.E. Bertels, S.P. Tolstov, V.V. .Braginsky, I.M. Mominov, B. Gafurov, I.V. Stebleva, A.O. Makovelsky, Y. Jumaboev, M. Ishakov, literary critics A. Qayumov, N. Mallaev, N.Rakhmonov, pedagogues-scientists O'.Aleuov, M.Orifiy and others include research.

The oldest monuments of education have not reached us directly. The spiritual culture monuments of the Turkic and Persian-speaking peoples, which emerged as a complex of wisdom and were recognized as examples of a practical approach to existence, are works such as "History" by the ancient Greek historian Herodotus, "Geography" by Strabo, and "Devonu dictionary-Turkish" by Mahmud Kashgari, as well as , preserved in literary-historical sources such as the Urhun-Enisei inscriptions and through them have reached us. The study of the nature of these monuments shows how material and spiritual culture played a big role in the formation of a person. In particular, education influenced the formation of a person intellectually and morally, and the formation of a person, in turn, helped the formation of a personal society. So, the process of ensuring the development of a person with the ability to think and the social development of society are formed in a mutual relationship. Knowing the nature of this historical process tells us that human thinking has been formed for a long time and in complex conditions. It is known that in the process of the creation of a human society, a person has improved both biologically and socially. The first religious beliefs, the improvement of the simplest inventions, etc., gave rise to the formation of the human mind. This process included thousands of years, and it was during this period that the rules of conduct and social requirements, which were accepted as the basis of the formation of human consciousness,

emerged. These requirements form the main content and essence of monuments created in a certain period.

The characteristics of the most ancient people, their initial, simple desires and hopes were expressed in the form of legendary characters and heroes reflected in ancient epics. The world of thought of our most ancient ancestors is reflected in legends and narratives, which cover religious beliefs and rituals such as spirit worship (animism), ancestor spirit worship (totemism), and sorcery. But these narratives and legends also express the spirit of the times when the Massagets, Sakas, Khorezmians, Sogds and Parthians lived.

In studying our oldest cultural assets, we rely on sources divided into the following three groups:

1. Exhibits found as a result of archaeological excavations.
2. Materials of folklore and written sources.
3. The creative heritage of great writers and scholars.

It is known that primitive people satisfied their needs in the process of labor activity, and this process prepared the ground for formation of theoretical knowledge, skills and competences in the young generation to work and start practical activities. In the beginning, the process of organizing labor activities was carried out on the basis of establishing the entire social life, then education became the main aspect of human activity, an important factor in the formation of social consciousness. Even before the primitive clan society, man struggled for survival, and in this period, all members of the clan acted as a team. Later, people organized labor activities according to the age of team members on the basis of the following three groups.

- a) children and adolescents;
- c) full participants in social life and work;
- s) the elderly.

In a primitive society, a child directly participates in the organization of activities that he can do, and acquires the skills of living and working. This situation happened in difficult conditions, while boys worked with men to hunt and make weapons, while girls learned the secrets of work performed by women. According to unwritten customs and traditions, young children would have certain experiences under the supervision of elders. After certain preparations, the child passed special tests and gained the right to actively participate in practical activities. This tradition, i.e. handing over children to a nanny or tutor until a certain age, was preserved until recent times, and is still visible today.

At the stage of the seed team, the scope of children's work expands, and the types of professional activities increase. Experienced people begin to teach children to write along with education. Gradually, the initial manifestations of military education begin to emerge. Teaching children the secrets of military art is a very complicated task, and the organization of this education required special knowledge and training. Therefore, people with special military knowledge and training began to be involved in the process of imparting knowledge in this regard to children.

The social progress of the society created the need to teach children about methods of measuring fields, preventing floods, and treating people from various diseases. As a result of the organization of the movement to meet this need, various schools began to operate. In schools, the main attention was focused on the formation of writing skills in children along with oral knowledge. At first, photography developed and pictographic letters appeared, then a method of writing with the help of letters introduced from neighboring countries appeared and this method began to spread rapidly. In the middle of the millennium BC, Aramaic, and after the conquest of Alexander the Great, Greek, as well as Persian cuneiform were used at certain times. By the middle of the first millennium BC, Avesta, Khorezm, Sogd, Kushan, Run (Urhun-Enisei), Uyghur and other scripts appeared on the basis of the Aramaic script and played an important role in the development of education.

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